

3 | 9 August 2025

ESFC LISBON

21st European Symposium
on Fluorine Chemistry

F

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

EMAIL

esfc.lisbon@chemistry.pt

WEBSITE

21-esfc-lisbon.events.chemistry.pt

NOVA SCHOOL OF
SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY

SOCIEDADE PORTUGUESA DE QUÍMICA

Book of Abstracts

21st European Symposium on Fluorine Chemistry

ESFC LISBON 2025

Lisbon, 3 – 9 August 2025

ISBN 978-989-8124-47-0

9 789898 124470

ESFC LISBON
21st European
Symposium on
Fluorine Chemistry

<https://21-esfc-lisbon.events.chemistry.pt/>

Activated Carbon for PFAS and Pharmaceutical Removal: A Sustainable Water Purification Approach

Beatriz P. Machado¹, Joana C. Bastos¹, Inês Matos¹, Maria Bernardes¹, João M. M. Araújo¹, Ana B. Pereira^{1,}*

(1) LAQV, REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal

**e-mail: anab@fct.unl.pt*

The increasing presence of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs), such as per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and pharmaceuticals, in environmental waters has raised significant concerns due to their persistence and potential toxicity. Traditional water treatment methods highlight the need for innovative solutions. Activated carbons (AC) have emerged as a promising adsorbent for the removal of CECs, owing to their high surface area and adsorption capacity.[1] However, the sustainability of AC production and its cost-effectiveness remain key challenges, especially when considering the environmental impact of its sourcing. This work focuses on characterizing the adsorption capacity of AC derived from biomass waste as part of a circular economy approach. The biomass is reused into activated carbon and its ability to adsorb PFAS and pharmaceutical contaminants from aqueous solutions is evaluated. Several parameters, such as adsorption kinetics, equilibrium, and capacity, are assessed under different conditions to determine the effectiveness of AC in removing these pollutants. The results demonstrated significant potential for removing CECs, including PFAS and pharmaceuticals, from environmental water. This approach not only offers a sustainable method for waste valorisation through circular economy principles but also provides an effective solution for tackling persistent water contamination. The promising adsorption capacity of biomass-based AC offers a pathway for more sustainable, cost-effective water treatment strategies.

References

[1] Mokhati, A., Benturki, O., Benturki, A., Fennouh, R., Kecira, Z., Bernardo, M., Matos, I., Lapa, N., Ventura, M., Soares, O. S. G. P., Rego, A. M. B. D., & Fonseca, I. Applied Sciences, 2022, 12(15), 7607.